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When to show confidence?

The interaction between CEO overconfidence and conveyed confidence in M&A announcements

Abstract

In this paper, we investigate the moderating effect of conveyed confidence on the relationship between CEO overconfidence and acquirer stock returns. Drawing on signaling theory as our theoretical lens, we argue that CEO overconfidence influences deal performance. Relying on the behavioral literature on CEO overconfidence we hypothesize that acquisitions helmed by overconfident acquirer CEOs yield negative acquirer stock returns upon announcement and that the level of conveyed confidence can dampen this effect. Based on original data that incorporates the financial data of the firms, their stock performance, and collect press releases for the focal deals, we test our hypothesis using a sample of mergers and acquisitions of public targets conducted by constituents of the S&P 500 from 2014 until 2020. Contrary to our baseline hypothesis, we do not find a negative relationship between CEO overconfidence and the acquirer stock returns. However, lower levels of conveyed confidence in the acquirer announcement communication lead to a significantly more positive stock return for overconfident acquirer CEOs. Our findings advance the literature on M&A announcements by looking into the level of conveyed confidence that is disseminated through the M&A announcement press releases as we address how individual factors and M&A communication work together to influence investors.

Keywords: Acquisitions; CEO overconfidence; Signaling Theory; Event Study;

1. Introduction

We're confident that, once regulators see the compelling benefits, they'll agree this is the right move at the right time for consumers and the country. April 29, 2018, joint press release for the T-Mobile-Sprint acquisition announcement retrieved from LexisNexis.

CEOs helming the next acquisition are commonly expected to convey confidence in the outcome of their recent strategic decision to pair up with others for the future. Overconfidence refers to a cognitive bias of substantial scholarly interest (Chen, Crossland, & Luo, 2015; Lee, Hwang, & Chen, 2017) and a widely observed phenomenon in human decision-making and M&A research at large (Lee et al., 2017; Malmendier & Tate, 2008). CEOs, as frequent decision-makers, are often prone to this bias (Heaton, 2002; Navis & Ozbek, 2016) and research on the influence of CEO overconfidence on firm performance outcomes has yielded mixed results (Chen et al., 2015; Galasso & Simcoe, 2011; Malmendier

& Tate, 2008; Navis & Ozbek, 2016). However, in the context of mergers and acquisitions (hereafter: M&A), the acquirer CEO's level of overconfidence is associated with negative short-term stock market reactions upon M&A announcement (Malmendier & Tate, 2008). On the other hand, deal-specific confidence, meaning the confidence of a CEO to generate value with a specific deal, represents a positive signal to investors (Gamache et al., 2018; Schijven & Hitt, 2012). Hence, the question arises how investors react to combinations of signals of CEO overconfidence and deal-specific confidence? Therefore, we investigated the moderating effect of conveyed confidence in the M&A announcement communication on the relationship between CEO overconfidence and acquirer announcement stock returns.

We draw on a behavioral conceptualization of investors and regard stock market reactions as an indicator for the overall investor sentiment triggered by the release of new information (Campbell, Sirmon, & Schijven, 2016; Schijven & Hitt, 2012). Both signaling theory and impression management offer powerful theoretical lenses to study the effects of disseminated information on investors' reactions to M&A announcements (Campbell et al., 2016; Graffin, Haleblan, & Kiley, 2016). In this paper, we draw on signaling theory and follow Vergne, Wernicke, and Brenner (2018: 811) who argue that "it may be more realistic to examine the drivers of signal credibility [hence, the relationship between signal and underlying quality (Connelly, Certo, Ireland, & Reutzel, 2011)] from the viewpoint of signal interpreters". This is especially interesting since scholars have begun assessing the effect of signal interaction, and in particular signal incongruence (Paruchuri, Han, & Prakash, 2020; Stern, Dukerich, & Zajac, 2014). While the aforementioned papers show the overall negative effects of signal incongruence, we set out to investigate a case in which signal incongruence might yield positive outcomes. While acquirer CEO overconfidence represents a negative signal to investors in M&A announcements, because of its increased likelihood to destroy value (Malmendier & Tate, 2008; Roll, 1986), deal-specific conveyed confidence represents a positive signal, indicating value creation (Schijven & Hitt, 2012). Our results indicate that lower levels of conveyed confidence are more positive in the case of higher levels of CEO overconfidence, showing that signal incongruence can yield positive effects for the acquirer announcement stock returns.

Following previous literature, we define CEO overconfidence as an acquired cognitive bias that fosters a CEO's belief to possess superior capabilities in deriving value from M&A deals. One key aspect of CEO overconfidence is its nature as a cognitive bias rather than an inter-individual disposition. Hence, overconfidence is acquired by a CEO rather than a manifestation of his or her personality (Billett & Qian, 2008). Therefore, the recent

experience of a CEO is likely to influence the level of overconfidence he or she possesses, which in turn influences the decision-making process (Hayward & Hambrick, 1997).

Regarding the deal-specific confidence, we draw on linguistic measures recently used in both management and finance to assess the level of conveyed confidence in documents (Lee et al., 2017; Loughran & McDonald, 2011). We analyzed the acquirer M&A announcement press releases to conduct this measure since press releases represent a medium that is widely followed by investors (Dyck & Zingales, 2003).

Our contributions to the literature are threefold. Firstly, indicators of the level of CEO confidence in the value-creating potential of an M&A event were found to influence investors' reactions upon M&A announcement (Malmendier & Tate, 2008; Schijven & Hitt, 2012). However, there is an ongoing debate to further shed light on the conditions influencing the relationship between CEO overconfidence and firm performance outcomes (Reyes, Vassolo, Kausel, Torres, & Zhang, 2020). We add to this by investigating how the conveyed confidence in the M&A announcement communication influences the aforementioned relationship, thereby, extending the literature on signal interaction and signal incongruence in particular. Secondly, research on M&A announcement effects has started to look into the influence of acquirer communication prior to and around M&A announcements. For instance, Graffin, Haleblan, and Kiley (2016) found that acquirers are more likely to disclose a higher frequency of positive yet deal-unrelated press releases prior to an M&A announcement that is anticipated to yield negative investor response. However, this research has not yet looked into the effects of the M&A announcement communication itself (Gao, Yu, & Cannella Jr, 2016). We aim to advance the literature here by looking into the level of conveyed confidence that is disseminated through the M&A announcement press releases. Thirdly, research drawing on behavioral theory has found various links between individual-level factors and M&A outcomes (Devers et al., 2020; Welch, Pavićević, Keil, & Laamanen, 2019). However, the M&A communication strategy has paid less attention to how individual factors and M&A communication work together to influence investors (de Groote et al., 2019; Devers et al., 2020).

2 Hypotheses

2.1 CEO overconfidence and its influence on M&A short-term stock market responses

Overconfidence represents a cognitive bias referring to a mismatch between perceived and reasonable levels of confidence (Moore & Healy, 2008). It leads individuals to have an unrealistic belief in their performance and predictions. Here, we look into the influence of CEO overconfidence, defined as an acquired cognitive bias that fosters a CEO's belief to

possess superior capabilities in deriving value from M&A deals (Hayward & Hambrick, 1997; Roll, 1986). Following, this line of research we expect to also find a negative relationship between higher levels of CEO overconfidence and investors' reaction to M&A announcements.

Hypothesis 1: A higher level of CEO overconfidence is associated with lower levels of short-term acquirer stock returns upon M&A announcement.

2.2 The conveyed confidence in firm disclosures – the influence of textual tone

While traditional signaling theory regards language-based signals as unreliable because senders face equal costs producing them (Bergh, Connelly, Ketchen Jr, & Shannon, 2014), this assumption is based on isolated substantive signals (Connelly et al., 2011). However, if analyzing multiple signals and their interactions, language has been found to influence the uptake of substantive signals (i.e. signals with a separating cost function) (Steigenberger & Wilhelm, 2018). One key aspect of language that was found to influence investors is the textual tone (Hossain, Raghunandan, & Rama, 2020; Huang, Teoh, & Zhang, 2014; Price, Doran, Peterson, & Bliss, 2012). In management science, the textual tone of documents was found to be associated with the level of confidence (Lee et al., 2017). Thereby, the level of conveyed confidence could influence the more substantive signal of CEO overconfidence by mitigating its negative effects.

Hypothesis 2: Lower levels of conveyed confidence in a firm's M&A announcement communication positively moderate the relationship between CEO overconfidence and short-term acquirer stock returns upon M&A announcement.

3 Methods

3.1 Sample

The opportunity to establish the empirical value of the above arguments is tested using Thomson SDC to build our acquisition sample. The initial population encompasses all mergers and acquisitions of public targets undertaken by constituents of the S&P 500 as of December 31, 2020. We refine this to include all M&As announced: (1) between January 1, 2014, and December 31, 2020; (2) which do not involve a recapitalization, repurchase of own shares, or a spin-off to existing shareholders; (3) in which the acquirer was seeking to buy 100% of the target shares at the announcement. This selection leaves us with a sample size of $n = 158$ deals, for which we calculated our variables. Our dataset is composed using different data sources. In addition, we used LexisNexis to collect acquirer press releases for the focal deals.

3.2 Analysis

To test our hypotheses, we estimated four robust ordinary least square (OLS) models. In all cases, we control for unobserved effects by including year dummies, and we correct for industry clusters using the acquirer SIC code to create major industry group dummy variables.

Dependent variable

Acquirer abnormal short-term stock market returns. We operationalized the investors' reaction using the conventional event study measure of short-term cumulative abnormal returns (CARs). Event studies using CARs are very common in acquisition research (Haleblian, Devers, McNamara, Carpenter, & Davison, 2009). They represent a good measure for gauging the overall market sentiment change as a consequence of the dissemination of new information (McWilliams & Siegel, 1997). In this paper, the CARs are calculated using a ten-day trading window, previously used in CEO overconfidence studies (Hayward & Hambrick, 1997).

Independent Variables

Level of CEO overconfidence. Following the literature on CEO overconfidence, we measured the level of CEO overconfidence, as the stock appreciation during the twelve-month prior to an M&A announcement, excluding the period in which we gathered our dependent variable (Hayward & Hambrick, 1997). *Level of conveyed confidence.* We built our measures of conveyed confidence based on the textual tone of firm communication in the acquisition announcement. More specifically, we analyzed the content of press releases using an automated linguistic approach that exploits dictionaries particularly developed by Loughran and McDonald (2011) for the analysis of financial text bodies. Firstly, we counted the number of negative words in a given document and standardized it by the total number of words in a document. This approach has recently been used to assess the level of confidence in various text bodies (e.g. Twitter account, earnings conference calls transcripts) (Lee et al., 2017). Secondly, we conducted a measure to be used in the robustness check. Following Huang et al. (2014) we calculated the textual tone of a document taking the difference between negative and positive words, and dividing it by the total number of words in a document (Hossain et al., 2020).

Main findings and contributions

Our results indicate that the influence of CEO overconfidence on the acquirer stock returns is moderated by the level of conveyed confidence in the M&A announcement communication. Hence, these two signals interact to influence investors. Moreover, lower levels of conveyed confidence (a positive signal of CEO deal-specific confidence) are more beneficial in the case of higher levels of CEO overconfidence. Therefore, we find interesting results of how signal incongruence can yield positive effects (Paruchuri et al., 2020; Vergne et

al., 2018). Moreover, while outside of the scope of our study, we find that conveyed confidence is explaining a substantive part of the acquirer stock returns, which is showing initial evidence for the effectiveness of language-based signals in M&A announcements (Steigenberger & Wilhelm, 2018). Interestingly, we find a positive influence of CEO overconfidence on the acquirer stock return in contrast to previous literature (Hayward & Hambrick, 1997; Malmendier & Tate, 2008). However, future research might profit from implementing additional measures of CEO overconfidence.

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Table 1. Descriptive statistics and correlations

	Mean	S.D.	(1.)	(2.)	(3.)	(4.)	(5.)	(6.)	(7.)	(8.)	(9.)	(10.)	(11.)
(1.) Cumulative abnormal return (-5,5)	0.641	4.270											
(2.) CEO overconfidence	2.478	1.976	-0.128										
(3.) Conveyed confidence	0.008	0.004	0.079	-0.094									
(4.) Acquisition premium (1 Week prior)	0.083	0.385	-0.023	0.009	-0.051								
(5.) Acquirer performance	-5.538	30.084	0.076	-0.092	-0.245*	-0.452*							
(6.) Acquirer debt-to-equity	0.881	1.587	-0.011	-0.041	0.103	-0.029	-0.052						
(7.) Geographic proximity	1.016	0.593	-0.013	-0.177*	0.019	-0.131	0.039	0.039					
(8.) Number of competing bidders	1.086	0.300	0.062	0.003	-0.140	-0.059	-0.042	0.054	-0.099				
(9.) Industry similarity	0.656	0.864	0.007	0.011	0.086	-0.051	-0.034	0.067	0.032	-0.010			
(10.) Merger of equals	0.011	0.103	-0.095	-0.025	0.030	-0.023	0.019	0.026	0.174*	-0.030	0.102		
(11.) Defense tactics	0.005	0.073	-0.006	0.169*	0.020	-0.015	-0.018	-0.041	-0.002	0.225*	0.115	-0.008	

* p < 0.05

N = 158

Table 2. Multiple regression (dummies for year and industry not reported). Dependent variable: acquirer's cumulative abnormal returns

	DV: acquirer's cumulative abnormal return (-5,5)			
	H1		H2	
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
Acquisition premium (1 Week prior)	-0.0004 (0.009)	-0.0005 (0.009)	-0.004 (0.009)	-0.001 (0.008)
Acquirer performance	0.006 (0.014)	0.003 (0.013)	0.002 (0.013)	0.004 (0.012)
Acquirer debt-to-equity	-0.099 (0.236)	-0.053 (0.226)	-0.109 (0.224)	-0.094 (0.207)
Geographic proximity	-0.823 (0.681)	-0.790 (0.650)	-0.823 (0.642)	-0.900 (0.592)
Number of competing bidders	-0.038 (1.263)	0.055 (1.205)	0.513 (1.210)	0.601 (1.115)
Industry similarity	-0.034 (0.436)	0.101 (0.418)	0.056 (0.413)	-0.030 (0.381)
Merger of equals	-1.930 (3.357)	-2.683 (3.210)	-2.542 (3.170)	-1.665 (2.927)
Defense tactics	0.092 (4.641)	0.228 (4.428)	-0.207 (4.377)	-0.497 (4.034)
	(1.376)	(1.317)	(1.313)	(1.211)
CEO overconfidence		0.047*** (0.013)	0.048*** (0.013)	0.022* (0.013)
Conveyed confidence			-195.741** (92.848)	-207.600** (85.606)
CEO overconfidence* Conveyed confidence				-12.723*** (2.585)
Constant	0.875 (1.602)	1.657 (1.543)	2.333 (1.557)	2.035 (1.436)
Observations	158	158	158	158
R ²	0.130	0.214	0.239	0.359
Adjusted R ²	-0.001	0.089	0.112	0.245
Residual Std. Error	4.268 (df = 133)	4.072 (df = 132)	4.020 (df = 131)	3.705 (df = 130)
F Statistic	0.992 (df = 20; 133)	1.707** (df = 21; 132)	1.874** (df = 22; 131)	3.164*** (df = 23; 130)

Note:

*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Figure 1. Estimated interaction effect